

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE FORMATION OF THINKING PROPERTIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: *This article discusses the use of educational technologies specific to today's globalization process.*

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INTRODUCTION

Today, the use of information technology in the educational process is accelerating, and it is clear that this has an impact on the better organization of the educational process. Therefore, the use of interactive methods in the educational process, the constant search for increasing the effectiveness of education has become a necessity of today, increasing the motivation of students to learn.

Accelerated development of economic and social spheres, full use of scientific and innovative potential with full mobilization of scientific, intellectual and financial resources, identification of priorities for future systematic reform of science, highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and independent thinking. In order to train and modernize the scientific infrastructure to a qualitatively new level, it is important to further strengthen the reforms in the educational process in the development of young people into harmoniously developed people.

The concept of education focuses on creating an individual's inner need for knowledge and teaching him to read, his inner experience, feelings, thinking. The importance of this work was emphasized by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov: "We have declared the education of the perfect man as a priority of state policy. When we say a perfect person, we mean, first of all, educated, enlightened people who are highly intelligent, able to think independently, and who set an example for others by their behavior.

Thus, the introduction of innovations in the education system, the effective use of modern pedagogical technologies is one of the important tasks of today's

education. Indeed, interactive methods increase the productivity of the educational process, shape the process of independent thinking of students, increase students' enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, solid mastery of knowledge, their free use in practice form skills and abilities. Thus, the introduction of innovations in the education system, the effective use of modern pedagogical technologies is one of the important tasks of today's education

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Interactive methods increase the efficiency of the educational process, form the process of independent thinking of students, increase students' enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, solid acquisition of knowledge, their free use in practice, form skills and competencies. It should be noted that education is one of the most complex types of human cognitive activity, which significantly accelerates individual mental development and the acquisition of knowledge. The teacher is not limited to imparting knowledge in the learning process, but also influencing the student in the process. This makes their learning more active. As a result, the student becomes an active participant in the learning process. Achievements in education depend primarily on the teacher.

Innovation is the creation of innovation, innovation. This means that the use of a form of work aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the educational process on the basis of news, rather than on the basis of the same templates as in traditional education, means innovation. Relying on pedagogical technologies and striving for innovation in education, the use of various interactive methods aimed at shaping the thinking skills of students will help to effectively achieve the goals of education.

Appropriate, purposeful, effective use of interactive methods by teachers in the process of education and upbringing. 'provides a wide range of opportunities to nurture the ability to synthesize, analyze, and find logical connections between different points of view.

Innovations, in turn, will be related to:

- Adoption of a new topic;
- Introduction of new processes;
- New content of the development area;
- New organizational forms of joint action;
- New management;
- New product etc.

For this reason, pedagogical innovation is now considered as a complex process, and its interactive qualities, educational parts, functional characteristics and membership are being studied. In this regard, if we use innovative educational

technologies in the teaching of psychology, the development of students' thinking will allow them to be formed at the level of established requirements.

This means developing students' thinking - science, technology, spirituality, education, art, etc., and raising their current status to a new level of quality. It is no secret that today the training of professionals who can achieve such results is very responsible and urgent. In particular, one of the main tasks of modern professionals is to constantly improve their intellectual potential in accordance with the level of development of society. To do this, in the organization of the educational process, it is expedient to use effective methods that allow students to actively participate in the educational process and work with interest, so that they master the basics of science. The use of a business game in shaping students' thinking skills gives high results. The main process of pedagogical technology is carried out in the form of educational lessons, ie pedagogical communication between teacher and student.

The use of business games demonstrates and develops students' ability to work independently, creatively and practically. Enrichment of previously acquired knowledge and skills, opportunities to apply in new situations.

Business or role-playing games are a type of challenging task. Only here, instead of textual material, is a life situation in which students play roles. Business and role-playing games serve the following functions as a learning method:

Instructor: Forming general education skills, developing creative ability, explaining, identifying and analyzing new situations.

Developer: develop logical thinking, speech, ability to learn about the environment.

Motivational: to motivate students to study, to come to an independent conclusion.

Educational: formation of responsible communication.

Implementation of game methods and situations in the prescribed form of training takes place in the following main areas:

1. Didactic goal is set for students in the form of tasks.
2. Learning activities are subject to the rules of the game.
3. Educational material is used as a tool.
4. Incorporate an element of competition into the learning activity that turns the didactic task into a game.
5. Successful completion of the didactic task is associated with the result of the axis.

How is a business game different from a role play? The participants of the business game are offered a game plot. In it, according to the described life

situation, participants are presented with one common goal of the activity: to solve the proposed problem.

At the same time, each participant must fulfill a separate role goal. Therefore, the process of developing a solution is individual-group in nature: each participant first decides on the purpose of his role, and then consults with the group. The fulfillment of this individual role goal depends on the outcomes of all team members. Typically, during a business game, problem solving occurs in several stages (2-3 to 10 per game). Evaluation of participants' performance is based on the indicators of the final and intermediate periods. Influencing the activities of the participants during the midterm assessment game allows them to independently perform the tasks set before them.

The final assessment takes into account the organizational activities of the students and their fulfillment of the role objectives of the role play.

The results show that the use of business games to enhance students' scientific outlook allows them to gain a number of educational advantages:

- A creative learning environment is created;
- the student is provided with quality and reliable educational and didactic and intellectual information, ie they are aware of the latest achievements of science and technology in their field;
- business game allows to ensure the use of computer programs in all types of training;
- creates conditions for independent learning, that is, it is one of the reliable methods in their professional activity, independence, acquisition of knowledge, and forms the knowledge, skills and abilities that need to be mastered.

The use of innovative technologies in the educational process is aimed at the comprehensive formation of students, through which the learning objectives are achieved, the exchange of object activities to the subject relationship, activation and pre-determination of the outcome. The remarkable aspect of such a game is that the future specialist takes a conscious and creative approach to improving their professional performance.

CONCLUSION

So, summarizing the above, it should be noted that the formation of a comprehensively mature person is one of the main tasks of today. The use of the game is a creative organizational and pedagogical activity, which can be used to create a promising and effective methodology of the educational process, as well as the training of competitive modern personnel, mentioned in the "National Program of Personnel Training."

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